

ieties released for general cultivation, only Mashuri and IR20 are adaptable.

Mashuri, called Ponni locally, has fine grain, yields 4-4.5 t/ha, and matures in 130 days. But it is highly susceptible to pests. Farmers in the region need a variety with the desirable traits of Mashuri plus high yield potential and pest resistance. With such a variety as the objective, Mashuri and IR8 were crossed and their segregating progenies were studied. A progeny line, P162, was released as PY1 Pudukai Ponni for general cultivation in 1979.

PY1 is a medium-duration variety that grows to 110 cm (Ponni or Mashuri grows to 120 cm). Its tillers are erect and compact, averaging 8 productive ones/hill. PY1 is tolerant of lodging and pests, and matures in 130 days. The color of the ripening spikelet is gold to

Mean yield of PY1 Pudukai Ponni compared with that of IR20 and Mashuri (Ponni) in the monsoon (Sep-Feb) season in Pondicherry Region, India.

Type of trials	Year	Yield (t/ha)		
		PY1	IR20	Mashuri (Ponni)
Trials at research stations	1977	5.1	3.5	3.5
	1978	4.8	1.9 ^a	4.1
	1979	6.5	4.1	5.3
Adaptive trials in farmers' fields	1977	6.0	4.2	4.8
	1978	4.7	4.3	4.3
	1979	5.5	4.8	—
General mean		5.4	4.2	4.4
		Yield difference (%) over IR20		
		+28.6	0	+4.8
		Yield difference (%) over Mashuri		
		+22.8	-4.6	0

^aSeverely affected by brown planthopper and virus; omitted in arriving at general mean.

brown. PY1's density and panicle length are almost identical to those of Ponni. The length-breadth ratio of PY1 grain is 3.0; that of Ponni is 3.2. The 1,000-grain weight of PY1 is 17.2 and that of Ponni

is 16.2 g. PY1's yields average 5.4 t/ha (29% higher than that of IR20, and 23% higher than that of Mashuri) (see table). ■

PY2 or Punithavathi — an early-maturing, fine-grained rice

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The Union Territory of Pondicherry, India, is an area of intensive rice culture under a rice-based multiple cropping system. Varieties up to 115 days in duration are raised during the dry seasons—January-April (*navarai*) and May-September (*sornavari*).

Because the duration of the varieties raised is 110-115 days, they cannot be fitted into the rice-based multiple cropping pattern. These varieties postpone planting subsequent crops on time. In addition, the farmers prefer fine-grain rice varieties with high yield potential because the traders and consumers prefer fine varieties.

All the short-duration varieties raised now during *navarai* and *sornavari* have coarse grains (long bold or short bold). Therefore, rice breeding at the Farm Science Centre seeks to develop varieties of less than 100 days duration with fine grain and high yield to profitably fit the rice-based multiple cropping system, where raising crops from January to September depends upon lift irrigation. This led to the identification of the

Mean yield level of PY2 or Punithavathi rice variety in the Pondicherry region, India.

Situation	Yield (t/ha) in				Mean
	1978 kharif (sornavari, May-Sep)	1979 rabi (navarai, Jan-Apr)	1979 kharif (sornavari, May-Sep)	1980 rabi (navarai, Jan-Apr)	
Rice Research Station	3.4 ^a	4.9	5.4	4.5	4.5
Adaptive trials at farmers' holdings	—	4.7	4.7	4.5	4.1
Demonstration in farmers' holdings	—	—	5.0	4.8	4.9
All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project trials (IET6972)	—	—	4.9	—	4.9
Lab to Land Program				4.8	4.8
Mean	3.4	4.8	4.8	4.6	4.8
Local check	1.8	2.5	4.2	—	—
	(CO 39)	(CO 39)	(ADT31)		

^aTrial was severely affected by brown planthopper.

P1275 line, which was released as PY2 (Punithavathi) in February 1980.

PY2 (Punithavathi) is a derivative from the cross between Kannagi (Puza 2-21) and Cult. 2032. It is a medium-dwarf variety like IR20. It grows to 90 cm in height and is resistant to the brown planthopper under field conditions. Tillers are erect, compact, and resistant to lodging. It matures in 95 days under transplanted conditions. The boot leaf is slightly broad, erect, and late in senescence. The grain type is fine (short slender) like TKM6 with the length-breadth ratio of 3.96. Grain weight is 18.5 g/1,000 grains and the rice is translucent white. The ripening color of the

glume is straw. The spikelet is green tipped. Punithavathi's average yield is 4.75 t/ha — minimum and maximum being 3.38 and 5.37 t/ha, respectively — superior to those of early and short-duration varieties tested (see table). ■

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